

Congolese Practice of tourism

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Abstract:

Background: Foreign practice tourism then nationals for lack of financial or culture, so it essential to analyze Congolese activities towards tourism.

Objective: This study describes the behavior of Congolese towards tourism, and studies Congolese expenditure for domestic and international tourism.

Materials and methods: From April 2014 to January 2015, the methodology of our study consists in six methods: historical, comparative, systemic, descriptive, inductive and analytical method. Moreover, for techniques, we used the free observation, the interview and the documentary technique.

Results: Congolese do indeed practice tourism but especially for the reasons of business, congress, official missions however the reasons for approval and leisure are few. This is the figure of 7% internally and at least 30% externally.

Conclusion: Congolese must be encouraged to practice internal tourism.

Keywords: Tourism, Practice, Congolese, International tourism, National tourism

I. Introduction

Tourism is an activity whose practice does not date from today. History tells us that the Egyptian pharaohs already practiced tourism in the Nile Valley. At that time, the important sights like the city of Alexandria, the pyramids, the temples of LUXOR, Thebes were already programmed in the touristic circuits (DECROOTE, 1989, p.11).

In 776 BC, the classic Olympic Games dedicated to Zeus were organized and attracted many curious people and travelers. The first inns date back to the 6th century BC.

The development of tourism is cited in the creation of universities such as Sorbonne, Oxford, Leuven ..., all this to show that tourism is an old tradition and that touristic motivations are numerous and varying according to times. Modern times are experiencing an explosion thanks to the development of means of transport.

In the 19th century, some interesting factors contributed to the development of tourism. These were the following:

- Technological progress;
- Men's Mobilities;
- The widening of the image of the world;
- Increased free time;
- Opening of borders;
- The rise in the standard of living;
- Holidays and paid leave (GUIBILATO, 1980, p.90).

Thus, from year to year until 1950, this activity (tourism) is practiced by the population in the entire world.

According to the statistics published by the *World Tourism Organization* (UNWTO, 1995), countries that emit tourists, are also the major receivers in the world market. These are mainly countries in the North of America, Mediterranean and Asia.

As a world phenomenon, developing countries, especially emerging ones, are following in the footsteps of these powers, which alone have $\frac{3}{4}$ basic infrastructures and which also share in terms of revenues $\frac{3}{4}$ of revenues generated by tourism.

Developing countries are characterized by a minor flow, a substantial lack of basic infrastructure and all that is needed to attract and secure international tourists (LOZATO-GIOTART, 2008, p.17).

Developed countries have an incentive policy that allows nationals to travel within their own territory to be the first visitors and consumers of sites, hotels, restaurants and all touristic products before foreigners because there is this culture of travelling and consequent means to realize it.

According to the *World Tourism Organization*(UNWTO, 1995), nationals must be encouraged to practice tourism. It recommends to the governments to facilitate to nationals the consumption of their touristic products with advantageous conditions, particularly hotels, restaurants, transports, touristic sites, museums, archives, botanical and zoological gardens and all other natural, historical and cultural curiosities in order to imbue the public with the culture of citizenship.

Unfortunately, many developing countries do not inculcate this culture to people who prefer to keep foreign tourists out of the business of earning the foreign exchange they need. Thus, nationals are not interested in these activities for lack of financial means or simply culture as we just said earlier.

Yet, it has been shown that the national demand is greater than the foreign one because in times of general crisis when international tourists do not come, tourism professionals fall back on nationals to cope with their charges while waiting for the release on the international plan.

However, considering the definition of tourism, one is ready to believe that everyone is doing or has already done tourism. This is the problem of this work because the UNWTO says "*tourism includes the activities of people traveling and staying in places outside their usual environment for an uninterrupted period of not more than one year for reasons of leisure, business, missions, and study or others.*" (UNWTO, 1995).

This important definition considers an environment as an area around its place of residence, plus all other places it wishes to visit when it comes to internal tourism. On the other hand, considering the different motives of displacement as a fundamental characteristic of the visit and the expenditure made by the visitors outside their home or abroad. We can, through all these factors, realize that Congolese have made tourism and spent significant sums in this activity both internally and internationally. This study can demonstrate it.

The objective of this study is twofold:

- To describe the behaviour of Congolese towards tourism, their way of travelling.
- To study, based on the survey, Congolese expenditure for domestic and international tourism.

Thus, we will determine:

- the expense generated;
- the reason for their stay;
- the age of traveler;
- the profession of traveler;
- who supports the trip.

To make the task more comprehensible, we will start with definitions of keywords without which understanding may cause problems to interpret or discussions.

II. Key Concepts

A. CHARACTERISTICS OF THE VISITOR

2.1. Visitors (RABORATOR, 2004, p.8)

Tourism includes the activities that people undertake during their travels and stays in places outside of their usual environment for a consecutive period of not more than one year for business and other recreational purposes.

These people are called "*visitors*". Therefore, any person who moves to a place outside his usual environment for a period of less than twelve months and whose main reason for the visit is other than performing a remunerated activity in the place visited.

2.2. Activity

The term "**Activity**" as used here refers to its general meaning. For example, a specific occupation that a person takes part in and not the meaning given to it when it is used in abbreviated ways to convey the idea of productive economic activity. As a result, visitors' activities relate to the occupations of people corresponding to the definition of visitors. It turns out that the term "tourism" cannot be defined by itself, regardless of who is involved in it (LANQUAR, 1990, p.26).

2.3. Classification of visitors

Countries can disaggregate their markets and further define them according to other characteristics of visits and their trips.

Two categories are created:

a) International visitors, whose country of residence is different from the country visited. This visitor category also includes nationals who are permanently resident abroad and who represent a significant segment of the market with specific characteristics.

b) Internal visitors, whose country of residence is the country visited, may be nationals or foreigners in a given territory.

A further distinction between forms of tourism in order to account for the difference between tourists and visitors of the day results in the following hybrid classifications:

- International visitors who spend the night;
- International visitors of the day;
- Internal visitors who spend the night;
- Internal visitors who of the day.

2.4. Usual environment (CACCOMO, 2002, p.125)

It is difficult to define in precise terms the usual environment needed to distinguish a visitor from all other travelers in a given country. Generally speaking, this environment corresponds to the geographical boundaries within which an individual move routinely with the exception of leisure and recreation.

The fact remains that a finding is necessary: if the place visited is not part of the usual environment of a person (visitor). The latter is not considered to belong to the group of usual resident consumers of these places.

Thus, students abroad, sick people or detainees who are more than one-year-old or more economically dependent on their family belong to their households while being residents in the place where their centre of interest is located but remain attached to their places where they live. Therefore, all these people are not visitors to the places where they live now. On the other hand, if other members of their households of origin move to come to see them, they will then have the quality of visitor of the places concerned.

2.5. Length of stay

To be considered as a touristic activity, a traveler's stay in a place he visits must be less than one year. As mentioned above, when a visitor stays at a place for more than a year, that place becomes part of his or her usual environment and the person ceases to be considered a visitor. In addition, people taking training courses or taking short-term stays (summer school, summer camp, short-term medical treatment) are considered as visitors to the place where the event takes place.

The UNWTO definitions distinguish two categories of visitors: tourists who must spend one or more nights in the place visited and visitors of the day who do not spend the night in the place visited.

Most visitors of the day are usually internal visitors but may also be international hikers. For example, crews and passengers of aircraft and boats that land in a country for less than one day passing immigration controls and are counted as international visitors of the day. This represents a significant proportion of tourism spending.

Finally, visitors legally "in transit" because they do not pass the national immigration controls meet all visitor characteristics and therefore there is no theoretical reason to exclude them from this category. However, to the extent that they do not officially return to the country, they do not appear in the national visitor statistics. There is no doubt that they represent an important market for the country concerned in terms of goods and services sold. Conscious of this situation, some airports have transformed transit areas into shopping malls, shops open in these areas are part of the economic territory of the country concerned, although it may be difficult to statistically identify passengers in transit, if their contribution for domestic tourism consumption is significant, appropriate statistical procedures should be used to measure it.

2.6. The reason for the visit (LOZATO-GIOTART, 2008, p.9)

In everyday language, the term "tourist" refers to individuals who travel for pleasure, for relaxation and holidays. However, the definition of a tourist selected by the Tourism Satellite Account is much broader and includes all individuals who travel or visit a place by spending one or more nights there for a reason other than to engage in paid activity in the place visited.

This definition is consistent with the concept of the usual environment since it corresponds to the place where a person usually lives and works. According to the definitions, visitors of UNWTO and according to the CST conventions, a person traveling for business or for commercial reasons can either be considered as a tourist or not.

Visitors and tourists of the day can be classified according to the main reason for their trips. The categories recommended by UNWTO are:

- Leisure, relaxation and holidays;
- Visits to relatives and friends;
- Business and professional reasons (including studies);
- Medical treatment;
- Religion and pilgrimage;
- Other airport and boat trips for public transport; transit and other activities.

2.7. Tourist consumption (BARMA, 2003, p.22)

In the same way that the visitor is at the centre of the touristic activity, its consumption is at the centre of the economic measure of tourism. The visitor is a particular type of consumer unit that differs from other households only in the fact that it is outside its usual environment or that it intends to leave that environment quickly, if not, this is an ordinary consumer so that the characteristics of consumption activity related to household consumption in the national accounts should also apply to visitors.

Thus, tourism consumption is the total expenditure of consumptions made by a visitor or on behalf of the visit for and during his journey and his stay in the place of destinations.

Consumption expenditure includes all goods and services acquired by or on behalf of the visitor. No goods or services of consumption can be excluded by their nature. If a product is acquired or used by a visitor during one or more trips or in preparation for a trip, it is excluded in the definition.

To conclude, in the basic definition used by the CST, tourism consumption includes:

- all consumption expenditure incurred during travel regardless of the nature of the goods and services concerned, only if they are goods and services of consumption;
- all service of consumption expenses (passport, vaccination, medical checks) and small items for personal use including gifts purchased before the trip, provided that their use is clearly and directly related to the trip;
- all consumption expenditure on goods and services made after the trip but clearly related to it (ROCHEFOUCAULD, 2007, p.97).

2.8. Place where the tourist expenditure is made

It is important to understand that tourism consumption is always linked to people who travel or plan to travel outside the usual environment.

The acquisition of goods and services may well be in the usual visitor environment, whether due to the nature of the good or service purchased (air ticket must be purchased in the usual environment even though is considered consumed during the trip) or the fact that this acquisition occurs before or after the trip but is clearly linked to it. It is therefore not very easy to determine the location of tourism consumption based on a visitor's itinerary or destination. We cannot be sure that all consumption expenditure of international visitors from sending tourism countries occurs in countries other than their country of residence. It is nevertheless important to locate these expenses geographically in order to analyze their impact on an economy that compiles. Therefore, it is necessary to distinguish the following aggregates based on the different forms of tourism:

- **Domestic tourism consumption** is a consumption that results directly from travel by visitors living within their own country. This consumption may include goods or even services produced abroad or by non-residents but sold in the domestic economy (imported goods) (ROCHEFOUCAULD, 2007, p.24).
- **Outbound tourism consumption** is a consumption that results directly from residents' trips to countries other than the one in which they reside. Purchases of international transport services are fully included regardless of the country of residence of the carrier (ROCHEFOUCAULD, 2007, p.98).
- **Inbound tourism consumption** is a consumption that results directly from the travel of non-resident visitors to and within the compiling economy.

In such cases, this consumption is limited to purchases made from suppliers who reside in the given economy. Transactions should be limited to those in which at least one stakeholder resides in the compiling economy.

- **national tourism consumption** = domestic tourism consumption + outbound tourism consumption;
- **consumption of international tourism** = consumption of inbound tourism + outbound tourism consumption.

By extension, the expense of visitors can be calculated in several ways, including and considering the ratios of volume and value variables. The simplest way to express the report for a given period is to calculate average expenditures per person-trip. Total expenditures for this period and for the intended tourism category are obtained from the following equation:

$$\text{Total tourism expenditure} = \text{Average tourism expenditure} \times \text{Number of person-trips}$$

It is also possible to obtain the best estimates of total tourism expenditure by using the average daily expenditure per person-trip and using the following equation:

$$\text{Total tourism expenditure} = \text{Average daily tourism expenditure} \times \text{Total number of overnight stays}$$

for the corresponding category of tourism during the period considered.

This number of overnight stays represents the length of stay in the country visited for international tourism and the total duration of the trip for national tourism and the total duration of the trip for domestic tourism. If we ignore this data, we can instead use the following equation:

$$\text{Total length of stay} = \text{Average length of stay} \times \text{Number of person-travelers}$$

which gives the total number of nights.

This method of calculating total visitors' expenditure can be considerably improved by calculating separate averages according to the categories to which visitors belong and the different characteristics of their trips and stays, since visitors' behavior changes, as the case may be.

The equations listed above can then be applied to each male and female group and it will be necessary to know all averages, corresponding numbers of person-trips or nights.

B. TOURISTIC OFFER (RABORATOR, 2004, p.37)

2.9. The characteristic products

The characteristic products are those which, in most countries, would cease to exist in significant quantities or whose consumption would decrease significantly, in case of absence of tourism and for which it seems possible to obtain the data.

2.10. The specific products of tourism

The specific products of tourism, it is the sum of the typical products of tourism and related products. The specificity of the products would therefore be associated with a special compilation. Thus, the WTO (UNWTO, 1995) list essentially includes services traditionally considered as touristic services because they meet the particular needs and wishes of visitors, accommodation, food, drinks, transport over a long distance, etc. associated services (including car rental) travel formalities, guide service, cultural and relaxation service.

2.11. Related products

Related products, that is, specific products that are not characteristic, would refer to different product categories: those found in most circumstances but of lesser importance, such as services those whose supply is specific to certain local characteristics of the place visited and would not necessarily be important elsewhere, such as handicrafts and souvenirs (RABORATOR, 2004, p.37).

2.12. Goods and services specific to tourism

According to the definition adopted, touristic consumption includes "any acquisition of goods and services by or on behalf of a visitor at the destination.

III. Study Area, Materials And Methods

3.1. Description of Study Area

This study was conducted in Kinshasa with third-level hotel and hospitality students, and second-year students in tourism and hotel management. Kinshasa has served us as a framework in that almost all executives, collaborators and agents of different public and private institutions regularly go to the provinces for various reasons and others go abroad as well are obtained in Kinshasa except for a few cases in Lubumbashi.

For some embassies, many businessmen are always when they can leave Kinshasa to go to the province to sell their products while many others go abroad, especially in Asia, to refuel in various clothing, home furnishing, home, car, hardware and other products. The advantages of Kinshasa are that it has one of the most frequented international airports by various airlines serving most countries of the world outside Lubumbashi.

3.2. Equipment

We used reams of paper to reproduce the survey questionnaires. During counting we made use of computers for data mining and calculators for the summation of figures in our possession.

3.3. Methodology of work

The methodology of this work includes the following methods and techniques:

3.3.1. Methods

The methodology adopted to maximize the chances of doing the job well consists of the following methods:

a) The historical method

Having worked on tourism which is an area still little known scientifically, it was useful to use this method to situate tourism in its origins, its peak and its future prospects

b) The comparative method

The comparative method allowed us to compare the different variables of touristic activity.

Thus, different variables length of stay, means of transport, age and sex were in light of this method.

c) Systemic method

The systemic approach has fundamentally focused on the assumption that the touristic phenomenon constitutes a totality and that the touristic facts must be seized because of the interdependence links that unite them.

d) The descriptive method

It allowed us to describe the entire history of tourism from its genesis to its peak in the 19th century.

e) The inductive method

The inductive method allowed us to start from particular cases to reach a law, a generalization.

f) The analytical method

The analytical method has been of considerable support especially in the collection, exploitation, analysis and interpretation of statistical data to our possession.

3.3.2. Techniques

Any research in a scientific application must include the use of rigorous and well-defined transmissible procedures and questions which may be applied again under the same conditions adopted to the kind of problems and phenomena in question. We used the following techniques:

a) Free observation on the ground

This technique allowed us to make field trips to meet the respondents in their living environment.

b) Interview

The interview is an observation process in which the interviewer seeks to obtain useful information by eliciting the oral statements of some people who may provide it. These are the members of Kinshasa community who have travelled abroad or in provinces.

c) Documentary technique

Enriching a scientific work requires a thorough reading. We have used the books published by the United Nations on tourism and the OMT which is its specific agency as well as the many authors to deepen our research, so we should add magazines, memoirs; theses, articles relating to a touristic phenomenon.

Our research began in April 2014 with free observation and surveys were demonstrated for nine months until January 2015. Our survey questionnaire was divided into two parts.

3.3. Justification of the survey

The survey techniques are valid for measuring touristic expenses, both for international tourism and for domestic (national) tourism. Expenses of visitors living abroad may be examined during their stay in or out of the country and by residents traveling abroad upon return to the country or when traveling abroad, they returned to their usual home.

Finally, the expense of residents who visit a region of their country can be observed during their touristic stays on the occasion of the return trip or when they have returned to their usual place of residence.

All surveys had a common focus on demand or consumption by referring directly to the amounts spent by visitors.

Surveys of touristic expenses on visitors have two characteristics:

- The survey can also be the possibility to estimate not only some averages but also the total expense of the population being surveyed using the direct or indirect expansion formulas appropriate to the desired purpose.
- The survey aimed at knowing touristic expense does not make it possible, given the methodology used or because of insufficient coverage or representativeness, that average expenses for each person per trip or per day, the quantity of which may be more or less good but in any case, requires the use of other amounts for weighting purposes and to be able to estimate the total expenditure.

It should not be forgotten that surveys not only make it possible to estimate expenses for all types of tourism but that they are practically the only way available to break down the expense by concept and to classify it according to the different characteristics of visitors, trips and stays by relating it to other touristic data observed simultaneously.

3.4. Counting, processing and interpretation of results

The counting, the processing and the interpretation of the results allowed us to classify the answers of the respondents, to check if the collected information is false or exact for their interpretation.

3.5. Difficulties encountered

We must denounce the novelty of the subject dealing with tourism in its particular aspect of travel and expenditure environments where this sector is not very developed and the mistrust of the respondent.

The misunderstanding of the question and answer off topic.

In terms of methodology, the level of people surveyed and their preparation for the concept of tourism to understand concepts before responding well was not easy.

These difficulties were overcome by the elimination of all the complacency responses, which allowed us to search the sample of 1000 instead of 1400 individuals for domestic tourism and 1000 instead of 1200 for international tourist emigration.

IV. Research Results

4.1. REGION VISITED

Table 1. Region visited by travelers

Provinces	f	%
Bas-Congo	362	36,1
Bandundu	156	15,6
Ecuador	103	10,3
Occidental Kasai	11	1,1
Oriental Kasai	44	4,4
Katanga	159	15,9
Maniema	23	2,3
North Kivu	55	5,5
Oriental Province	85	8,5
South Kivu	2	0,2
Total	1000	100,0

Source: our field surveys in 2015

In view of Table 1 on frequencies in the provinces, we note that for the period of our study considered, 36% of the respondents went to Bas-Congo, 15.6% to Bandundu, 15.9% to Katanga, 10.3 % in Ecuador and 0.2% in South Kivu. Thus, it emerges from this study that the community of Kinshasa is in majority in Bas-Congo and less in Kasai and South Kivu from the point of view of internal tourism.

Table 2. Countries visited by travelers

Continents	f	%
Africa	359	35,9
America	111	11,1
Asia	271	27,1
Europe	259	25,9
Total	1000	100,0

Source: our field surveys in 2015

In Table 2 at the international level, 35,9% of Congolese visitors remain in Africa during their travels, particularly in RSA, Mali, Benin, Congo Brazza city and, to a lesser extent, Kenya and Rwanda, 25,5% went to Asia, especially to China, Turkey, India and Dubai, while 11% were gone to Americas including Canada, the US and to a lesser extent Brazil.

The mobility of Congolese during this period was important especially in Asia for business and in the provinces for the reasons of important commercial activities as will probably be demonstrated by the analysis of the different reasons for stays on these trips.

4.2. AGE

Table 3. Age of visitors to internal tourism

Travelers age	f	%	mi	nimi
15 à 24	7	0,7	19,5	136,5
25 à 44	297	29,7	34,5	10246,5
45 à 64	372	37,2	54,5	20274
65 à 84	324	32,4	74,5	24138
Total	1000	100,0		54795

Source: our field surveys in 2015

In terms of domestic tourism, we note that travel ages are: 37, 2% between 45 and 64, 29.7% between 25 and 44, 65 to 84 32%.

Table 4. Age of visitors to international tourism

Travelers age	f	%	mi	nimi
De 0 à 14	4	0,4	7	28
De 15 à 24	41	4,1	19,5	799,5
De 25 à 44	671	67,1	34,5	23184
De 45 à 64	275	27,5	54,5	14987,5
de 65 à 84	8	0,8	74,5	596
Total	1000	100,0		39595

Source: our field surveys in 2015

At the international level, between the ages of 25 and 44, 67.1% and 27% are between 45 and 64 years of age. To some extent, 4% of children move with parents. The departure abroad between 65 and 84 is almost zero.

4.3. SEX

Table 5. Gender of Visitors to Domestic Tourism

Travellers gender	f	%
Male	559	55,9
Female	441	44,1
Total	1000	100,0

Source: our field surveys in 2015

About Visitors to Domestic Tourism, Sex is an important characteristic, so we find that 55.9% of the men internally compared to 44.1% moved internally as shown in TABLE 5.

Table 6. Gender of visitors to international tourism

Travelers gender	f	%
Male	589	58,9
Female	411	41,1
Total	1000	100,0

Source: our field surveys in 2015

Sex is an important characteristic to international tourism travel, so we find that 58,9% of men also went abroad against 41% of women in TABLE 6.

4.4. PROFESSIONAL CATEGORY

Table 7. Occupational category of visitors to internal tourism

Travelers Occupational	f	%
Entrepreneur, individual trader	278	27,8
Liberal profession, senior manager, professor	156	15,6
Middle manager, teacher	51	5,1
Employee, worker	186	18,6
Student	198	19,8
Retired, inactive	23	2,3
Other	108	10,8
Total	1000	100,0

Source: our field surveys in 2015

Regarding the socio-professional category, as indicated above, 27,8% of internal trips are individual activities and 15,8% are administrative tasks while 19% are for studies according to Table 7.

Table 8. Occupational category of visitors to international tourism

Travelers Occupational	f	%
Entrepreneur, individual trader	287	28,7
Liberal profession, senior manager, professor	189	18,9
Middle manager, teacher	74	7,4
Employee, worker	150	15,0
Student	119	11,9
Retired, inactive	18	1,8
Other	162	16,2
Total	1000	100,0

Source: our field surveys in 2015

In view of Table 8 internationally 28,7% are also liberal professionals while 18.9% are officials on missions and 16,2 for other reasons.

4.5. DURATION OF THE STAY

Table 9.Length of stay of visitors to national tourism

Duration	f	%	mi	nimi
0 à 7	363	36,3	3,5	1270,5
8 à 15	239	23,9	11,5	2748,5
16 à 23	80	8,0	19,5	1560
24 à 31	143	14,3	27,5	3932,5
32 à 39	175	17,5	35,5	6212,5
Total	1000	100,0		15724

Source: our field surveys in 2015

As shown in Table 9, 36% of in-house travelers make 7 days while 23% make 2 weeks 7, 5% stay longer.

Table 10. Length of stay of visitors to international tourism

Duration	f	%	mi	nimi
0 à 7	318	31,8	3,5	1113
de 8 à 14	267	26,7	11	2937
15 à 23	136	13,6	19	2584
24 à 31	140	14,0	27,5	3850
32 à 39	140	14,0	35,5	4970
Total	1000	100,0		15454

Source: our field surveys in 2015

Internationally, 31,8% are one week old while 26.7% are two weeks and 14% are longer.

4.6. REASON

Table 11. Reasons for travel to national tourism

Reasons	f	%
Business	230	23,0
Mission	193	19,3
Vacation	76	7,6
Family visit	140	14,0
Other	361	36,1
Total	1000	100,0

Source: our field surveys in 2015

In view of Table 11, 23% left for business, 19% for missions, only 7,6% for holidays and 36% for other internal reasons.

Table 12. Reasons for travelers to international tourism

Reasons	f	%
Professional reason	366	36,6
Leisure, holidays	303	30,3
Other	331	33,1
Total	1000	100,0

Source: our field surveys in 2015

At the international level, 36,6% left for professional reasons combining business and missions while 30,3% went on vacation especially to South Africa, Angola and Congo Brazzaville and a small part in Europe. Many also internationally do not give the exact reason because most do not return. Others who have not found on the grounds cited theirs are forced to write other because of the ideal non-assistance.

4.7. MODE OF TRANSPORT

Table 13. Mode of transport of visitors to national tourism

Mode of transport	f	%
Air	432	43,2
Sea	60	6,0
Railway	57	5,7
Bus	202	20,2
Personal car	189	18,9
Other	60	6,0
Total	1000	100,0

Source: our field surveys in 2015

With respect to transportation 43,2% of domestic tourists used the plane although the province in Central Kongo had a lot of travelers but its overall average is lower than those who went to other provinces by using the plane. 20% used their own vehicle and 20% by bus as shown in Table 13.

Table 14. Mode of transport of visitors to international tourism

Mode of transport	f	%
Air	943	94,3
Sea	45	4,5
Personal car	4	0,4
Other	8	0,6
Total	1000	100,0

Source: our field surveys in 2015

Internationally, 94% of travelers went by plane and a minimum group by boat to Brazzaville. Others to Angola by their own car as shown in Table 14.

4.8. ACCOMMODATION

Table 15. Mode of accommodation of visitors to national tourism

Hosting Mode	f	%
Hotel	561	56,1
Other	439	43,9
Total	1000	100,0

Source: our field surveys in 2015

Most of the Congolese who travel indoors also reside in hotels, others in the family or in similar establishments as among religious as indicated in Table 15.

Table 16. Mode of accommodation of visitors to international tourism

Hosting Mode	f	%
Hotel	698	69,8
Supplementary accommodation	21	2,1
Camping, caravanning	29	2,9
Rented furniture	41	4,1
Second home	101	10,1
Other	111	11,1
Total	1000	100,0

Source: our field surveys in 2015

At the international level also about 70% of travelers stay in hotels, 21% most often in India and China in forms of dormitories where women get together and 41% in rented buildings as in India and 24% as in RSA remain with family members also in particular forms of rented residence (see Table 16).

4.9. ACCOMMODATION EXPENSES

Table 17. Accommodation expenses of visitors to national tourism

Expenses	f	%	mi	nimi
0 à 49	159	15,9	24,5	3895,5
50 à 99	76	7,6	49,5	5662
100 à 149	60	6,0	124,5	7470
150 à 199	46	4,6	174,5	8027
200 à 249	46	4,6	224,5	10327
250 à 299	37	3,7	274,5	10156,5
300 à +	234	23,4	324,5	75933
Total	657	65,7	-	-
Missing system	343	34,3	-	-
Total	1000	100,0	-	121471

Source: our field surveys in 2015

From Table 17, we note that, depending on the class, 15.1% spend at least \$ 50, 7.6% spend at least \$ 100 and 65.7% spend \$ 300 for housing. This gives an average of \$ 121 for each.

Table 18. Accommodation expenses of visitors to international tourism

Expenses	f	%	mi	nimi
de 0 à 249	201	20,1	124,5	25024,5
de 250 à 499	242	24,2	374,5	90629
de 500 à 749	123	12,3	624,5	76813,5
de 750 à 999	119	11,9	874,5	104065,5
de 1000 à 1249	218	21,8	1124,5	245141
Total	903	90,3	-	-
Missing system	97	9,7	-	-
Total	1000	100,0	-	541673,5

Source: our field surveys in 2015

In Table 18, we note that 20% spend at least \$ 250, 24.2% spend at least \$ 500 and 21.8% spend at least 1250 for accommodation for a long time.

4.10. RESTORATION EXPENSES

Table 19. Restoration expenses of visitors to national tourism

Expenses	f	%	mi	nimi
0 à 99	349	34,9	49,5	17275,5
100 à 199	133	13,3	149,5	19883,5
200 à 299	57	5,7	249,5	14221,5
300 à 399	80	8,0	349,5	27960
400 à 499	55	5,5	449,5	24722,5
500 à 599	5	0,5	549,5	2747,5
Total	680	68,0	-	-
Missing system	320	32,0	-	-
Total	1000	100,0	-	106810,5

Source: our field surveys in 2015

Generally, people who travel internally do not spend a lot of money if they stay with their family, but when the stay is extended, you can have this expense increased. The proportions are as follows: 34.9% spend at least \$ 150, 13% spend at least \$ 200 and 5% spend \$ 450 when the stay is very long.

Table 20. Restoration expenses of visitors to international tourism

Expenses	f	%	mi	nimi
de 0 à 99	133	13,3	49,5	6583,5
de 100 à 199	205	20,5	149,5	30647,5
de 200 à 299	179	17,9	249,5	44660,5
de 300 à 399	127	12,7	349,5	44386,5
de 400 à 499	287	28,7	449,5	129006,5
Total	932	93,2	-	-
Missing system	68	6,8	-	-
Total	1000	100,0	-	255284,5

Source: our field surveys in 2015

In Table 20, expenses are broken down as follows: 13% spend \$ 100, 20% spend \$ 200, 17% spend \$ 300 and 28% even arrive at \$ 500, especially in European or American countries.

4.11. VARIOUS PURCHASES

Table 21. Various purchases of visitors to national tourism

Expenses	f	%	mi	nimi
De 0 à 49	218	21,8	24,5	5341
50 à 99	99	9,9	74,5	7375,5
100 à 149	71	7,1	124,5	8839,5
150 à 199	16	1,6	174,5	2792
200 à 249	48	4,8	224,5	10776
300 à 349	23	2,3	324,5	7463,5
350 à 399	11	1,1	374,5	4119,5
400 à 449	14	1,4	424,5	5943
450 à 499	7	0,7	474,5	9381,5
500 à 549	143	14,3	524,5	75003,5
Total	651	65,1	-	-
Missing system	349	34,9	-	-
Total	1000	100,0	-	130975

Source: our field surveys in 2015

Through various purchases, we are waiting for shopping, souvenirs, clothing and more. On the domestic front, Congolese also spend a lot to resell or consume in the interior of the country. As shown in Table 21, 21% of Congolese spent \$ 50 for this and 14% spent at least \$ 500 on various food purchases, squash, caterpillars, fish, plants, etc. Some buy bags that they put in trucks or boats (hinge) to sell.

Table 22. Various purchases of visitors to international tourism

Expenses	f	%	mi	nimi
0 à 249	355	35,5	124,5	44197,5
250 à 499	125	12,5	374,5	46812,5
500 à 749	125	12,5	624,5	78062,5
750 à 999	60	6,0	874,5	52470
1000 à 1249	255	25,5	1124,5	286747,5
Total	920	92,0	-	-
Missing system	80	8,0	-	-
Total	1000	100,0	-	508290

Source: our field surveys in 2015

In view of Table 22 those who go abroad to China, India, Dubai, RSA, Europe and America make important purchases. Thus 35.5% spent at least \$ 350, 25.5% spent up to \$ 1250 for clothing, gifts, souvenirs, appliances for their own needs and the needs of their family.

4.12. TOTAL EXPENSES

Table 23. Total expenses of visitors to national tourism

Expenses	f	%	mi	nimi
0 à 1499	811	81,1	749,5	607844,5
1500 à 2999	166	16,6	2249,5	373417
3000 à 4499	23	2,3	3749,5	86238,5
Total	1000	100,0	-	1067500

Source: our field surveys in 2015

It is difficult for anyone to say exactly and accurately all the expenses involved in a trip, but according to this survey 81% of Congolese traveling in the interior spent between \$ 0 and \$ 1500 and a small minority spent between \$ 1,500 and \$ 3,000, especially for the purchase of property to resell in Kinshasa.

Table 24. Total expenses of visitors to international tourism

Expenses	f	%	mi	nimi
0 à 1500	154	15,4	750	107800
1500 à 3000	314	31,4	2250	706500
3000 à 4500	216	21,6	3750	8100000
4500 à 6000	148	14,8	5250	777000
6000 à 7500	168	16,8	6750	1134000
Total	1000	100,0	-	3535300

Source: our field surveys in 2015

For those who go abroad especially in China, Dubai, India and Istanbul, 15% spend at least \$ 1,500 while 31% spend at least \$ 3,000 and 14% spend between \$ 4,500 and \$ 6,000 depending on the property to buy and the business activity. We can see vehicle purchase, furniture materials in China, hardware store in Istanbul etc. freight transportation by freight in China.

4.13. TRAVEL FUNDING

Table 25. Funding of visitors to national tourism

Funding	f	%
<i>Tourist himself</i>	536	53,6
<i>Employer in the city visited</i>	179	17,9
<i>Employer in the city of provenance</i>	285	28,5
Total	1000	100,0

Source: our field surveys in 2015

The care is very important because it determines the origin of the resource that gave the opportunity to the tourist or visitor to make this trip. In tourism, it is essential for the marketing to easily and accurately grasp the origin of the means that allowed the traveler to make his trip. That also goes with the socio-economic status of visitor.

Internally, as shown in Table 25, 54% of travelers made the trip at their own expense while 28.5% were supported by their employers in the city of origin, 17% were supported by the employer of the city visited.

Table 26. Funding of visitors to international tourism

Funding	f	%
<i>Tourist himself</i>	571	57,1
<i>Employer in the country abroad</i>	179	17,9
<i>A social organization</i>	119	11,9
<i>Other</i>	131	13,1
Total	1000	100,0

Source: our field surveys in 2015

Internationally, according to Table 26, 57% of travelers are self-employed and have supported themselves, while 18% by their employers and 11% by social organizations. Note that 13% do not determine the origin of their resource.

4.14. Table of synthesis

Table 27. Summary Table of National Tourism

Variable	f	%	Average
Age	1000	54795	54,7
Length of stay	1000	15724	15,7
Accommodation expenses	1000	121471	121,47
Meal expenses	1000	106810,5	106,81
Travel expenses	1000	18734	18,73
Entertainment expenses	1000	10797	10,79
Various purchases	1000	130975	130,97
Total expenses	1000	1067500	1067,5

Source: our field surveys in 2015

Table 28. Summary Table of International Tourism

Variable	f	%	Average
Age	1000	39595	39,59
Length of stay	1000	15454	15,45
Number of travellers	1000	1894,5	1,89
Travel expenses	1000	953250	953,25
Accommodation expenses	1000	541673,5	541,67
Meal expenses	1000	255284,5	255,28
Exceptional expenses	1000	249960,5	249,96
Current expenses	1000	225362	225,36
Various purchases	1000	508290	508,29
Total expenses	1000	3535300	3543,3

Source: our field surveys in 2015

Conclusion

During this research, which questioned whether Congolese were doing tourism at the national or international level, we conclude that given the theories related to this activity and considering all the practices, Congolese do indeed tourism on the one hand and the other. They spend both internally and externally large amounts on these trips.

Using the direct observation method, it is necessary to use measured frequencies, other methods and other surveys to evaluate touristic activity in general and average daily expenditure or per person-trip expense if we want to avoid having to make direct calculations of the total receipts and expenditures of national or international tourism by means of the banking method and to make appropriate readjustments during the years which separate the two respondents, these will have to in any case, be close enough.

We conclude at the end of this study that Congolese do indeed practice tourism but especially for the reasons of business, congress, official missions however the reasons for approval and leisure are few. This is the figure of 7% internally and at least 30% externally.

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